

CENTRAL ASIA REGION: A THREAT TO ITS SECURITY SOURCES AND MEASURES TO FIGHT AGAINST THEM

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Abstract. *The countries of the region are pursuing an active foreign policy to achieve peace and sustainable development in Central Asia. Making Central Asia a zone of peace and good neighborliness has also been identified as a priority of Uzbekistan's foreign policy. The relevance of this article is that at a time when the sources of global threat are increasing, ensuring regional security in Central Asia has become one of the main tasks facing the countries of the region. Areas of trade and economic, transport and transit-logistics, security and stability, completion of issues related to state borders, equitable use of water resources, strengthening cultural and humanitarian ties, friendship and good neighborly relations between nations are being developed between the two countries. Among them, the main task of the article is to provide a comprehensive analysis of the directions and joint initiatives related to peace and security, especially in Central Asia. The Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, states that the formation of security, stability and good neighborliness around Uzbekistan is a priority of our foreign policy in the near and medium term and increased efficiency. The article also concludes that the geopolitical and geostrategic importance of the Central Asian region has been growing in recent years, due to its vast mineral and raw material resources, it is gaining serious attention in the international arena and the region is experiencing a conflict of strategic interests. In composing this article, comparative comparison, theoretical and general logic methods were used. The article consists of an introduction, main part, conclusion and a list of references.*

Keywords: regional security, social balance, interethnic conflicts, drug trafficking, religious extremism, border issue, water issue.

ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОАЗИАТСКИЙ РЕГИОН: УГРОЗА ИСТОЧНИКАМ ЕГО БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ И МЕРЫ БОРЬБЫ С НИМИ

Аннотация. *Страны региона проводят активную внешнюю политику для достижения мира и устойчивого развития в Центральной Азии. Превращение Центральной Азии в зону мира и добрососедства также было определено в качестве приоритета внешней политики Узбекистана. Актуальность данной статьи заключается в том, что в условиях возрастания источников глобальной угрозы обеспечение региональной безопасности в Центральной Азии стало одной из основных задач, стоящих перед странами региона. Между двумя странами развиваются направления торгово-экономической, транспортно-транзитно-логистической, безопасности и стабильности, решения вопросов, связанных с государственными границами, справедливого использования водных ресурсов, укрепления культурно-гуманитарных связей, дружбы и добрососедских отношений между народами. Среди них основной задачей статьи является всесторонний анализ направлений и совместных инициатив, связанных с миром и безопасностью, особенно в Центральной Азии. В Стратегии действий по пяти приоритетным направлениям развития Республики Узбекистан на 2017-2021 годы, принятой Президентом Республики Узбекистан, указано, что формирование*

безопасности, стабильности и добрососедства вокруг Узбекистана является приоритетом нашей внешней политики. в ближайшей и среднесрочной перспективе и повышение эффективности. В статье также делается вывод о том, что геополитическое и геостратегическое значение Центрально-Азиатского региона в последние годы возрастает, в связи с его обширными минерально-сырьевыми ресурсами, он привлекает к себе серьезное внимание на международной арене и регион переживает конфликт стратегических интересов. При составлении данной статьи использовались методы сравнительного сравнения, теоретического и общелогического методов. Статья состоит из введения, основной части, заключения и списка литературы.

Ключевые слова: *региональная безопасность, социальное равновесие, межэтнические конфликты, наркотрафик, религиозный экстремизм, пограничный вопрос, водный вопрос.*

INTRODUCTION

The regional political processes and regional security topics are new as an object of scientific research at the beginning of the 20th century appeared within such disciplines as political science and regional studies. Analysis of existing approaches to defining the concept of regional policy that they are theoretically insufficiently developed shows. In addition, they are more focused on the internal politics of countries. In our opinion, the policy of ensuring regional security the complexity of the concept of the region should be taken into account in the analysis. because it involves a multi-part structure, that is, regional politics in the interpretation of the relationship between the center and the subregions, as well as manifested at the "macro region" level. Available changes and updates development vector of each region, social and political forms the self-management ability of subjects, as well as impact on the process of emergence of threats to peace and security.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Regional security problems in the Central Asian subregion as well terrorism, extremism, weapons of mass destruction, as in the whole world spread, increasing the risk of nuclear weapons, drug business, environment degradation, global warming, deforestation, pandemic diseases outbreaks and other threats. Water resources the risk of wars related to distribution is also increasing. also Many old countries of this region have an internal, endogenous character and for new problems they still do not find a suitable answer. Including internal political and socio-economic instability, inter-ethnic conflicts between regional elites and state-run structures existing contradictions, population impoverishment, population the increase in the difference in income and the increase in social balance, high level of unemployment among young people, the rise of corruption receiving, low efficiency of state structures, any political a worldly ruler ready to raise his head when instability occurs active from social problems to discredit the administrations user of radical Islamism, drug trafficking and religious the growth of the influence of extremism and the continuity of the supreme political power problem (because this is the case in most of the countries of Central Asia there are no clearly defined and established rules for duration) as the main threats to regional peace today appearing¹.

Controversies related to interstate conflicts also continue is doing. it is primarily a competition for water and energy resources is the "energy delimitation" problem caused by In particular, On the transboundary waterways of the Amudarya and Syrdarya - in connection with

the construction of Rogun HPP in Tajikistan and Qambarota HPP in Kyrgyzstan tensions arose. These projects are of particular concern to Uzbekistan because the water in the rivers as a result of the construction of these hydroelectric plants the possibility of a decrease in flow is very high.

Secondly, there are unresolved border conflicts in Central Asia are becoming serious security issues. These disputes directly affecting most of the republics of the region.

High ethnic diversity in Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan, lack of generally recognized borders, lack of land and most important is the depletion of water resources in arid climates a particular socio-economic dimension to recurring conflicts is giving Tensions between these republics have increased in recent years. Relations deny the emergence of new ethno-territorial conflicts can't. Their social basis is the constant growth of the population and difficult is formed according to the socio-economic situation. Third, interstate conflicts in the territory of unfinished nation statehood and the state inciting complex processes of forming ideologies. Their component is often territorial claims against neighbors or made to gain regional control of the state are turning into claims.

RESULTS

External as well as domestic problems are piling up rapidly influences and threats to ensure security in Central Asia has a significant negative impact. Among them, cross-border crime, terrorism and the growth of drug trafficking and in Afghanistan the return of the Taliban to power and the center of radical Islamism rotation is the most acute external for the peace of the region in the near future remains one of the effects.

It is known that the geographical position of the Central Asian region has both positive and negative aspects. On the one hand, the subregion trade routes between the countries North and South, East and West is located at the intersection, which is very useful from an economic point of view. on the other hand, the territory of these countries is strong neighbors- in the north Located between Russia, China to the east, and the troubled Islamic countries of Afghanistan, Iran, and Pakistan to the south and southwest. Also, with the Central Asian countries gaining independence.

A geostrategic problem that was not noticed before is that of Central Asia geographical isolation was more clearly manifested, that is, the region is world political and directly to international waterways located along economic flows can't get out. For this reason, the countries of Central Asia considering their geopolitical positions, on the one hand, and not only with each other, but also with powerful neighbors (primarily Russia, China) establish cooperation with, on the other hand, the world market trying to find new ways out. A series in the region

The leaders of the countries also tried to restore the Great Silk Road are doing Trade and economic cooperation over the past 30 years Certain conditions have been created for expansion. In particular, Azerbaijan, An opportunity to develop cooperation with Afghanistan and other countries providing Turkmenistan-Iran, Kazakhstan-China and a number of other routes. Railways and transport routes were launched. in 2010 Kazakhstan is 62nd in the ranking of countries by logistics indicators 1st place, Uzbekistan - 68th place, Kyrgyzstan - 91st place, Turkmenistan - 114th and Tajikistan took 131st place. But the main geopolitical of the region feature and advantage is its possession of the richest raw material reserves, they are one of the main reasons why world powers are interested in the region became one. Explored oil reserves have been identified in the world about 2.7% of the reserves, and gas - 7%. the world about 25% of uranium reserves and 8% of world production It corresponds to Kazakhstan.

At the same time, there are also territorial issues in ensuring the development of the region plays an important role. the artificial nature of the borders of the Central Asian countries is becoming a serious destabilizing factor in international relations and today it is of the countries and the Central Asian region as a whole it is kept as one of the factors that pose a threat to political stability remains. the most serious issues in this field are Kyrgyzstan - Uzbekistan,

A certain area between Tajikistan and Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan characterized by the presence of conflicts. In particular, there is a large joint border between Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan despite the delimitation of its part, there are about 100 disputed plots and an agreement has not yet been reached on them. and Tajikistan It has been claiming a part of the border regions of Kyrgyzstan, where mainly Tajiks live. Unilateral demarcation of borders and attempts to mine them constantly among the countries of the region causing a certain tension. in Central Asia a constructive approach to solving ethno-territorial and border problems necessary. water in Central Asian countries with an agrarian economy lack of water resources, the problem of its distribution and from them also brings usability issues to the fore. Watering system failure, lands where water is not used wisely irrigation, rapid growth of the population of Central Asian countries, water increasing the need for resources and the existing potential for conflict going with them.

DISCUSSION

Another one that is increasingly influencing the situation in Central Asia A global threat is the drug problem and cross-border distribution corridors the volume of drugs transported through, and drugs the number of consumers is also increasing every year. to European markets the transport corridor for the delivery of medicine passes through this region.

Artery of the countries of the region with Afghanistan proximity helps. For this reason, Western countries opium the increase in the demand for drugs by groups in Central Asia increasing the effectiveness of the corridor for drug trafficking. It should be noted that poverty and unemployment in Central Asia increase more and more people, especially women, youth and children leading to easy involvement in the drug business. in Tajikistan 10 of the total number of people convicted for drug trafficking in 2000 percent were women. The situation is also with Afghanistan Weakness of borders, corruption in border and customs authorities is also complicated by the high level. The geopolitical characteristics of Central Asia are powerful on a global scale countries in terms of the development of their economic relations and military-strategic cooperation with the countries of the region encourages to do. The region of Afghanistan, Pakistan, Iran and other Asia The fact that it is located at the intersection of countries is a factor of instability for the region despite creating cooperation with the republics of this region development of other Asian countries globally and regionally can provide important guarantees in achieving security. One of the main tasks of the USA, Russia and China is leadership in the region position and prevent the merger of the remaining two countries.

At the same time, the interests of these three countries in the region are mutual is both compatible and opposite. Conflicting interests (terrorism, the fight against drug trafficking, etc.) USA, China and Cooperation of Russia with the countries of Central Asia creates the need. Conflicting interests each of these three countries to the conclusion of separate agreements with the countries of Central Asia or the bilateral actions of Russia and China within the SCO leads to coordination.

In June 2018 in Samarkand "Central Asia: one past and common "Partnership for the

Future, Sustainable Development and Mutual Prosperity". at the international conference between the five countries of Central Asia discuss existing problems, risks and, most importantly, prospects for cooperation done Forum of 10 leading international organizations, primarily Held with the support of the United Nations, there are more than 500 participants from 20 countries participants attended. The main of such a representative meeting one of the topics is security problems in the region, in the water-ecological sphere cooperation, prevention of dangers and threats in Central Asia assistance, as well as defining prospects for mutual cooperation in the future was to get

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev at the conference "Our common goal is to make Central Asia stable and economic turning it into a developed and prosperous region. For this that we combine national perspectives with regional priorities, conditions and reasons that create and feed conflicts we have to destroy it," he emphasized. Security issues theses devoted to the speech of the head of Uzbekistan, mainly his UN.The last lecture he gave from the pulpit was to support young people, believers developing and strengthening the true values of Islam in the mind, also combined with the final solution of border problems. Thus, the head of Uzbekistan is once again the security of Central Asia He mentioned the most priority directions for fighting terrorism and extremism expressed his position on the fight, and also to the neighbors at some point to forget the existing contradictions and as they say suggested moving to constructive regional cooperation. High on foreign affairs and security policy of the European Union

Representative Federica Mogherini on security issues in Central Asia paid special attention because, according to him, the Middle East and The situation in Afghanistan is not only close to these hotbeds of tension worries its neighbors, but also Europe. That's why Old the world is strongly interested in Central Asia. At the same time, Mogherini becoming someone's reputation in the global game of world empires that the countries of the region should be independent in order not to remain emphasized. The continues to talk about the regional security of Central Asia as we are, the word almost all parts of the world, neighboring Afghanistan, Pakistan, Starting with India, Iran, and China, Japan and the USA can be seen in the distance can end with Every country in the Central Asian projects sees its participation in specific directions. It should be noted here that external actors in Central Asia active participation is often described as the new great game. Some according to the analysis of experts, if Russia, China, the USA, the European Union, if there are geopolitical games between turkey, iran, india and pakistan, all of them are mainly from energy reserves in Central Asia will be used. However, the region is only large countries preventing it from being accepted as a field of geopolitical struggle between There are other factors. First, the managers of Central Asia not only are they subject to external actors, but they are also against each other.They themselves decide to cooperate with a certain "player".Second, regional in addition to energy security in Central Asia from internal threats to political security to stability, ethnic ranging from conflicts and poor inter-regional relations.There is a long list of threats to the negative effects coming from Afghanistan list is available. Abdulaziz Komilov, the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Uzbekistan, said that now.Central Asian countries together in the 21st century friendship, good neighborliness and cooperation for the purpose of development is preparing a five-way interstate document.

CONCLUSIONS

The above analyzes and experience of donors in Central Asia. The four main priorities in the field of security are as follows: security reforms, border control, crime fighting and in-depth analysis of the situation. In the case of Uzbekistan, it is possible to work on all items. Border control and crime cooperation with the governments of China and Russia on countermeasures. It is necessary to start. Safety net reforms are a gradual process. For donors with known risks, this aspect of the case is a complex issue is counted because the countries of the region in some of their actions for themselves they see a clear threat. Therefore, programs in this field that it is not dangerous to work out and help the security structures it is necessary to act with confidence. In particular, SCO regional security, economic development of cooperation, terrorism, separatism, extremism, to combat the threats of drug trafficking and organized crime directed. Other organizations in the region and peace and stability for intergovernmental dialogue on collective regional security will become an important area for the formation of the system.

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